

Master Thesis

Aerial Camera-Based Localization Using Deep Learning Methods

Judit Hermán

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Supervisors: Dr. András Benczúr,

Dr. Csaba István Sidló

HUN-REN Institute for Computer Science and Control, Artificial
Intelligence Laboratory

Thesis advisor: Dr. Roland Molontay

Department of Stochastics

BME Institute of Mathematics

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1 Introduction

The task of UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) localization based on camera images in GPS-denied environment is becoming increasingly widespread in the field of computer vision. Localization is essential for autonomous navigation along predetermined routes or dynamically reacting to changes in the environment. Additionally, UAVs must avoid collisions and dangerous situations, which also requires reliable localization. UAVs are widely used, but they largely rely on GPS; however, they may occasionally lose the GPS signal [1].

The IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit) sensors measure the acceleration and roll, pitch, and yaw angles of the drones, which can be used to predict their position, but over extended periods, this method may become inaccurate due to the accumulation of errors. The availability of camera images offers a potentially more reliable method for localization, especially when ground-truth satellite images or images taken with the same camera during previous drone flights are available, as these can be used to train deep learning models [1].

However, real-time camera-based localization faces many challenges. The basic idea is to train a deep learning model on the ground truth images off-line, then make the drone determine its location instantly when it takes a new image based on the trained model and the baseline images. For this, the model and the images should be small enough to fit into the drone's memory, and the model should be fast enough to provide real-time results. That is why autoencoders are often used, because the encoded vectors can be stored instead of full-size images [1]. Another difficulty is that the landscape can change if the pictures are taken at a different time of day or in a different season. Hence, the season-invariant UAV localization is an essential aspect of the problem [2]. Using infrared cameras instead of visible light cameras can improve performance at relatively short distances in low visibility conditions, such as fog or smoke [3].

In my thesis, I will begin by providing an overview of the theoretical background of the methods I used to solve the UAV localization problem. Next, I will discuss the various approaches presented in the scientific literature on this topic. Then I will describe the data I worked with and the methods I used, including the models and evaluation techniques. Finally, I will show my results, draw conclusions, and mention some possible future directions.

2 Theoretical Background

2.1 Introduction to Neural Networks

Artificial Neural Networks are machine learning models inspired by the structure and function of nerve cells in the human brain. They contain layers of interconnected units, called neurons, that transform input data through weighted connections and nonlinear activation functions [4].

2.1.1 Structure of Neural Networks

A neural network typically contains an input, an output, and usually a certain number of hidden layers with the following roles:

- **Input layer:** Receives the raw data (e.g. pixel values of an image).
- **Hidden layers:** Perform computations and feature extraction.
- **Output layer:** Produces the final prediction.

Each neuron computes a weighted sum of its input values and applies a nonlinear activation function:

$$z = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i + b, \quad a = \phi(z),$$

where w_i are the weights, x_i are the inputs, b is the bias, and ϕ is the activation function (e.g. sigmoid, ReLU, tanh) [4].

Figure 1: Illustration of a neural network. Source: <https://cs231n.github.io/neural-networks-1/>.

2.1.2 Forward Propagation

During forward propagation, the input is passed through each layer, and outputs are computed layer by layer until the final prediction is obtained.

2.1.3 Loss Function

The loss function measures the difference between the network's prediction and the true target value. Common loss functions include:

- **Mean Squared Error (MSE)** for regression:

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$$

- **Cross-Entropy Loss** for classification:

$$\mathcal{L} = - \sum_{i=1}^n y_i \log(\hat{y}_i),$$

where \hat{y}_i 's are the predictions and y_i 's the true values.

2.1.4 Backpropagation and Learning

The backpropagation algorithm aims to minimize the loss function by updating the weights of the network. It works by applying the chain rule of calculus to calculate the gradient of the loss function with respect to each weight:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial w_{ij}} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial a_j} \cdot \frac{\partial a_j}{\partial z_j} \cdot \frac{\partial z_j}{\partial w_{ij}}$$

These gradients are used to perform gradient descent:

$$w_{ij}^{(t+1)} = w_{ij}^{(t)} - \eta \cdot \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial w_{ij}}$$

where η is the **learning rate**, a hyperparameter controlling the step size during optimization. A lower learning rate ensures slower but stable convergence with the risk of getting stuck in a local optimum, while a higher learning rate results in faster learning but risks overshooting the minimum value.

Training Process: The network is trained iteratively:

1. Passing input data through the network (forward propagation),
2. Computing the loss,
3. Performing backpropagation to compute gradients,
4. Updating weights using gradient descent.

This cycle is repeated over many epochs until the network learns to generalize well on unseen data [4].

2.1.5 Transfer Learning

Transfer learning exploits the representations learned by a model on a source task to improve performance on a target task, especially when the latter has limited labeled data. Mathematically, given a source domain \mathcal{D}_S with task \mathcal{T}_S and a target domain \mathcal{D}_T with task \mathcal{T}_T , transfer learning aims to improve the learning of the target predictive function $f_T(\cdot)$ using knowledge from \mathcal{D}_S and \mathcal{T}_S , where $\mathcal{D}_S \neq \mathcal{D}_T$ or $\mathcal{T}_S \neq \mathcal{T}_T$ [5].

In practice, this often involves:

- Freezing the lower layers of a pre-trained network (e.g. convolutional filters in image tasks),
- Fine-tuning the upper layers or task-specific heads,
- Using the pre-trained model as a feature extractor.

Transfer learning is particularly effective when the source and target tasks are semantically related, as the internal representations (features) learned in the source domain can be meaningfully reused [6].

2.2 Autoencoders

Since I used autoencoders to address the UAV localization problem, I will first provide an overview of what autoencoders are and how they function based on Umberto Michelucci’s paper “An Introduction to Autoencoders” [7]. The article covers the mathematical and fundamental concepts of autoencoders, including their definitions, limitations, typical use cases, and some examples. It begins with a general introduction to autoencoders, then discusses the role of the activation function in the output layer and the loss function. It also explains the concept of reconstruction error in detail. In addition, it mentions typical applications such as dimensionality reduction, classification, denoising, and anomaly detection.

2.2.1 Definitions

Autoencoders are usually used when we have unlabeled observations x_i for $i = 1, \dots, M$ in the training dataset

$$S_T = \{x_i | i = 1, \dots, M\}.$$

The observations are in general $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^n$ with $n \in N$. Autoencoders were first introduced by Rumelhart, Hinton, and Williams in 1986 [9]; they aimed to learn to reconstruct the input observations x_i with the lowest error possible. For example,

if we have a dataset of images, an autoencoder is an algorithm that can output an image that is as similar to the input as possible. The authors used the following definition of autoencoders:

Definition 2.1 (Autoencoder). *An autoencoder is a type of algorithm with the primary purpose of learning an “informative” representation of the data that can be used for different applications [10] by learning to reconstruct a set of input observations well enough.*

The autoencoders have the following three main components: an encoder, a latent feature representation, and a decoder, as shown in Figure 2. The encoder and decoder are simply functions, and the latent feature representation typically means a tensor of real numbers. In general, we aim to reconstruct the input well enough. Still, at the same time, it should create a latent representation (the output of the encoder part in Figure 2) that is useful and meaningful. For example, latent features on hand-written digits could be the number of lines needed to write each number or the angle of each line, and how they connect. This latent representation can then be beneficial for various tasks (e.g. feature extraction that can be used for classification or clustering) or simply understanding the essential features of a dataset [7].

Figure 2: General structure of an autoencoder; source: [7]

Typically, both the encoder and decoder are neural networks. The encoder can be expressed as a function $g : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^q$,

$$h_i = g(x_i), \quad (1)$$

where $h_i \in \mathbb{R}^q$ is the latent feature representation, the output of the encoder block in Figure 2 when it is evaluated in the input x_i . The decoder $f : \mathbb{R}^q \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ (and the output of the network indicated by \hat{x}) can be written as a function of the latent features:

$$\hat{x} = f(h_i) = f(g(x_i)), \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$. Training an autoencoder means finding the functions $g(\cdot)$ and $f(\cdot)$ that satisfy

$$\underset{f,g}{\operatorname{argmin}} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^M \Delta(x_i, f(g(x_i)))}{M}, \quad (3)$$

where Δ indicates a measure of how the input and the output of the autoencoder differ (basically, the loss function penalizes the difference between input and output).

Adding a bottleneck is commonly used when creating autoencoder networks; it is achieved by making the dimension of the latent feature lower (often much lower) than that of the input [7].

Regularization in autoencoders. In this case, regularization means enforcing sparsity in the latent feature output. The most common way of regularization is to add an ℓ_1 or ℓ_2 regularization term to the loss function. The ℓ_2 regularization term looks like this:

$$\underset{f,g}{\operatorname{argmin}} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^M \Delta(x_i, f(g(x_i)))}{M} + \lambda \sum_i \theta_i^2, \quad (4)$$

In the formula, the θ_i 's are the parameters of the functions $f(\cdot)$ and $g(\cdot)$. In the case of neural networks, the parameters are the weights [7].

2.2.2 Feed-Forward Autoencoders

A Feed-Forward Autoencoder (FFA) is a neural network made of dense layers with a specific architecture. A dense layer is simply a set of neurons that get their input from the previous layer. Each neuron in a dense layer receives as input the output of all neurons in the previous layer. Typically, an FFA network has fewer and fewer neurons in its layers moving to the center of the network and has a symmetric structure. The middle layer is called the bottleneck, and it usually contains fewer neurons than the size of the input. In almost all practical applications, the layers after the middle one are a mirrored version of the layers before the middle one. The layers up to and including the middle one make the encoder part of the model, and the layers from and including the middle one (up to the output) make what is called the decoder.

In case of successful FFA training, the result is a good approximation of the input ($\hat{x}_i \approx x_i$). The decoder can reconstruct the input using only a much smaller number (q , the latent dimension) of features than the input observations initially have (n). The output of the middle layer h_i is also called a learned representation of the input observation x_i [7].

Activation Function of the Output Layer. In case of neural network-based autoencoders, the activation function of the last layer plays an important role. The most common choices are ReLU and sigmoid.

1. ReLU

The formula of the ReLU activation function is:

$$\text{ReLU}(x) = \max(0, x). \quad (5)$$

If we use ReLU, all values should be in the range of $[0, \infty]$. The author emphasizes that the usage of this function is appropriate when the input observations x_i assume a wide range of positive real values.

2. Sigmoid

The sigmoid activation function can be written in the following formula:

$$\sigma(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}. \quad (6)$$

The sigmoid function can only be used if the input values x_i are in the range of $]0, 1[$ or if they were normalized before.

Loss Function. To train a neural network, we need a loss function to minimize. The loss function in this case will be

$$\mathbb{E}[\Delta(x_i, g(f(x_i)))].$$

The two most widely used loss functions for autoencoders are Mean Squared Error (MSE) and Binary Cross-Entropy (BCE).

1. Mean Squared Error

The most common choice for a loss function is the Mean Squared Error (MSE), because the autoencoders solve a regression problem:

$$L_{MSE} = MSE = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M |x_i - \hat{x}_i|^2. \quad (7)$$

L_{MSE} can be used in almost all cases, independently of how we choose the activation function of the output layer or whether the data is normalized. L_{MSE} is minimal if $\hat{x}_i = x_i$. If the inputs are 1-dimensional, it can be easily proved by calculating the derivative of L_{MSE} with respect to a specific observation j . The minimum is found when the condition

$$\frac{\partial L_{MSE}}{\partial x_i} = 0$$

holds for all $i = 1, \dots, M$, because $\frac{\partial L_{MSE}}{\partial x_i} = -\frac{2}{M}(x_j - \hat{x}_j)$, which is equal to 0 when $x_j = \hat{x}_j$. Since $\frac{\partial^2 L_{MSE}}{\partial \hat{x}_j^2} = \frac{2}{M} > 0$, it is indeed a minimum value.

2. Binary Cross-Entropy

We can use the binary cross-entropy as a loss function when the activation function of the last layer of the FFA is a sigmoid function, which limits the output values between 0 and 1, and the input features are normalized between 0 and 1 as well. It is usually used for classification problems, but it also works for autoencoders.

$$L_{CE} = -\frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^n [x_{j,i} \log \hat{x}_{j,i} + (1 - x_{j,i}) \log(1 - \hat{x}_{j,i})], \quad (8)$$

where $x_{j,i}$ is the j^{th} component of the i^{th} observation. The sum is over the entire set of observations and all components of the vectors. Minimizing this loss function is equivalent to reconstructing the input as accurately as possible. Let us consider the simplified case where \mathbf{x}_i and $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i$ are one-dimensional. In this case, we use the notation x_i and \hat{x}_i henceforth. To find the minimum of L_{CE} , we need to solve the set of M equations

$$\frac{\partial L_{CE}}{\partial \hat{x}_i} = 0$$

for $i = 1, \dots, M$ to show that the binary cross-entropy L_{CE} is minimized when $x_i = \hat{x}_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, M$.

If we calculate the derivative of L_{CE} with respect to a specific input \hat{x}_j , we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial L_{CE}}{\partial \hat{x}_j} &= -\frac{1}{M} \left[\frac{x_j}{\hat{x}_j} - \frac{1 - x_j}{1 - \hat{x}_j} \right] = -\frac{1}{M} \left[\frac{x_j(1 - \hat{x}_j) - \hat{x}_j(1 - x_j)}{\hat{x}_j - \hat{x}_j^2} \right] \\ &= -\frac{1}{M} \left[\frac{x_j - \hat{x}_j}{\hat{x}_j - \hat{x}_j^2} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Now we can see that the condition $\frac{\partial L_{CE}}{\partial \hat{x}_i} = 0$ is satisfied only if $x_i = \hat{x}_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, M$. To make sure that this is a minimum, we need to calculate the second derivative as well. For the point to be a minimum value, the second derivative needs to be positive at that point:

$$\frac{\partial^2 L_{CE}}{\partial \hat{x}_j^2} > 0. \quad (10)$$

The second derivative at the minimum point $x_j = \hat{x}_j$ is

$$\left. \frac{\partial^2 L_{CE}}{\partial \hat{x}_j^2} \right|_{x_j = \hat{x}_j} = -\frac{1}{M} \left[\frac{x_j(2\hat{x}_j - 1) - \hat{x}_j^2}{(1 - \hat{x}_j^2)\hat{x}_j^2} \right] = \frac{1}{M} \left[\frac{\hat{x}_j(1 - \hat{x}_j)}{(1 - \hat{x}_j^2)\hat{x}_j^2} \right] \Big|_{x_j = \hat{x}_j}. \quad (11)$$

At the definition of this loss functions the author mentioned that the input and output values must be between 0 and 1: $\hat{x}_j \in]0, 1[$. It can be easily seen that

the denominator of the previous formula is greater than zero, the numerator is also greater than zero since $1 - \hat{x}_j > 0$, and this is why the values should be in the range $]0, 1[$. Dividing two positive numbers gives a positive number, which proves that

$$\frac{\partial^2 L_{CE}}{\partial \hat{x}_j^2} > 0, \quad (12)$$

so the binary cross-entropy loss function has a minimum value at $x_i = \hat{x}_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, M$ [7].

2.2.3 Autoencoder Applications

Dimensionality Reduction. Using autoencoders with a bottleneck layer means a reduction in the dimension of the input n observations to q dimensions ($q < n$). The trained encoder part of these models produces q real numbers, the latent features, which can be used for various tasks. The author highlights some advantages of the autoencoders compared to the PCA (Principal Component Analysis) method [8] in relation to dimension reduction. It is beneficial regarding computational efficiency because it can be trained with mini-batches, while the PCA algorithm uses the whole dataset during training. PCA projects a dataset on the eigenvectors of its covariance matrix, providing a linear transformation of the features. In contrast, autoencoders are more flexible and can also use nonlinear transformations of the features. The default PCA method uses $O(d^2)$ space for data in \mathbb{R}^d , which is often not computationally feasible, and the algorithm does not scale up with increasing dataset size. It is a very important aspect when facing a practical problem with a very large amount of data or a very large number of features.

FFA is equivalent to PCA if the following conditions are met¹.

- The encoder $g(\cdot)$ is a linear function;
- The decoder $f(\cdot)$ is also a linear function;
- MSE is used as a loss function;
- The input values are normalized with this formula:

$$\tilde{x}_{i,j} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{M}} \left(x_{i,j} - \frac{1}{M} \sum_{k=1}^M x_{k,j} \right).$$

¹We note that this is not a very well-known result and it has a long proof that can be found in the notes by M.M. Kahpra for the course CS7015 (Indian Institute of Technology Madras) at this link: https://www.cse.iitm.ac.in/~miteshk/CS7015_2018.html

Classification. Autoencoders can also be useful for image classification by applying training models on the latent features $g(x_i)$ instead of all input features (every pixel value of the images). Using latent features can reduce training time by multiple orders of magnitude while losing only a few percent in accuracy.

Anomaly Detection. Anomaly detection can also be performed using autoencoders. An autoencoder model trained on a given dataset, will not be able to reconstruct an image belonging to a totally different dataset, which means that the outliers can be found based on the reconstruction error [7].

2.2.4 Convolutional Autoencoders

Convolutional Autoencoders (CAEs) are a specialized type of autoencoder designed to process data with a grid-like topology, such as images. Unlike traditional autoencoders that use fully connected layers, CAEs employ convolutional layers in both the encoder and decoder components, enabling them to capture spatial dependencies and local patterns more effectively. The encoder uses these layers to create a compact representation from input images, while the decoder employs deconvolution layers for image reconstruction [11].

The encoder contains convolutional layers, each followed by an activation function (e.g., ReLU) and pooling layers that reduce the spatial dimensions of the input while increasing the depth of feature maps [12]. The decoder contains deconvolutional layers. Deconvolutional filters may be transposed versions of the convolutional filters. Additionally, each deconvolutional layer must be followed by an unpooling layer. The unpooling operation is performed by storing the locations of the maximum values during pooling, preserving the values of these locations during unpooling, and zeroing the rest [13].

CAEs have demonstrated significant utility in various applications, including image denoising, where they learn to remove noise from corrupted images, and dimensionality reduction, where they compress high-dimensional data into lower-dimensional representations while preserving essential information [14].

2.3 Generative Adversarial Networks

In their foundational paper, Goodfellow et al. [15] introduce Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), a novel framework for training generative models using a game-theoretic approach. The key innovation lies in formulating the training process as a two-player minimax game between two neural networks: a generator and a discriminator. The generator network (G) is designed to capture the data distribution and generate new data instances that resemble samples of the training set. In contrast,

the discriminator network (D) attempts to distinguish between real data samples (drawn from the true data distribution) and fake samples generated by G . D and G are differentiable functions represented by multilayer perceptrons. The generator learns to produce increasingly realistic data to deceive the discriminator, while the discriminator simultaneously improves its ability to detect synthetic data.

Mathematically, D is trained to maximize the probability of assigning the correct label to both training examples and samples from G , and simultaneously G is trained to minimize $\log(1 - D(G(z)))$. So the training objective is expressed as a minimax optimization problem:

$$\min_G \max_D V(D, G) = \mathbb{E}_{x \sim p_{\text{data}}(x)}[\log D(x)] + \mathbb{E}_{z \sim p_z(z)}[\log(1 - D(G(z)))]. \quad (13)$$

Here, x is a real data sample, $p_{\text{data}}(x)$ denotes the real data distribution, $p_z(z)$ is a prior distribution over the input noise variables, and $G(z)$ represents the data generated from the noise vector z and $D(x)$ outputs the probability that x is real. The discriminator outputs a probability indicating whether a given input is real or generated.

The authors demonstrate both theoretically and empirically that, under ideal conditions with sufficient model capacity and training time, the generator can learn to replicate the true data distribution. In equilibrium, the discriminator is unable to distinguish real from generated data, outputting a probability of 0.5 for all inputs.

2.3.1 Cycle GAN

The paper “Unpaired Image-to-Image Translation using Cycle-Consistent Adversarial Networks” by Jun-Yan Zhu et al. [16] introduces CycleGAN, a framework that enables image-to-image translation without the need for paired training data.

Traditional image-to-image translation methods, such as pix2pix, require paired datasets (e.g. a photo and its corresponding sketch). However, such paired data is often unavailable. CycleGAN addresses this limitation by learning mappings between two domains using unpaired datasets, making it applicable to a broader range of tasks.

CycleGAN employs two main components:

1. Adversarial Loss: Two generators, $G : X \rightarrow Y$ and $F : Y \rightarrow X$, along with their respective discriminators, D_Y and D_X , are trained adversarially. Each generator aims to produce outputs indistinguishable from the target domain, while each discriminator aims to differentiate between real and generated images. The adversarial loss for G and D_Y is $\mathcal{L}_{\text{GAN}}(G, D_Y, X, Y) = \mathbb{E}_{y \sim p_{\text{data}}(y)}[\log D_Y(y)] + \mathbb{E}_{x \sim p_{\text{data}}(x)}[\log(1 - D_Y(G(x)))]$.

2. Cycle Consistency Loss: To ensure meaningful mappings, CycleGAN introduces a cycle consistency constraint. This means that an image translated from one domain to another and then back again should closely resemble the original image: $F(G(x)) \approx x$ and $G(F(y)) \approx y$. This loss helps to preserve the content and structure of the original images during translation. The cycle consistency loss can be formulated as $\mathcal{L}_{\text{cyc}}(G, F) = \mathbb{E}_{x \sim p_{\text{data}}(x)}[\|F(G(x)) - x\|_1] + \mathbb{E}_{y \sim p_{\text{data}}(y)}[\|G(F(y)) - y\|_1]$.

The full objective function is:

$$\mathcal{L}(G, F, D_X, D_Y) = \mathcal{L}_{\text{GAN}}(G, D_Y, X, Y) + \mathcal{L}_{\text{GAN}}(F, D_X, Y, X) + \lambda \mathcal{L}_{\text{cyc}}(G, F), \quad (14)$$

where λ controls the relative importance of the two objectives. Using these notations CycleGAN model aims to solve the equation

$$G^*, F^* = \arg \min_{G, F} \max_{D_X, D_Y} \mathcal{L}_{\text{GAN}}(G, D_Y, X, Y) + \mathcal{L}_{\text{GAN}}(F, D_X, Y, X) + \lambda \mathcal{L}_{\text{cyc}}(G, F). \quad (15)$$

Figure 3: The operation of the CycleGAN model containing two mapping functions $G : X \rightarrow Y$ and $F : Y \rightarrow X$, and associated adversarial discriminators D_Y and D_X . D_Y ensures that G transforms X into outputs indistinguishable from domain Y . The role of D_X is similar for F . The middle image shows the forward cycle-consistency loss $F(G(x)) \approx x$, the right image the backward cycle-consistency loss $G(F(y)) \approx y$. Source: [16]

3 Related Work

There is a wide and continually growing range of UAV localization-related articles in the scientific literature. The work of Mollie Bianchi and Timothy D. Barfoot [1] provided the baseline for my research.

They aimed to solve the UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) localization problem in real-time, with low storage and computational cost. They approached the task using a convolutional autoencoder trained off-line on grayscale Google Earth images. Only the encoded vector representations of these images were stored in the UAV’s memory, enabling faster processing and reduced storage needs. The architecture of their convolutional autoencoder, shown in Figure 4, included convolutional and batch normalization layers and reduced the image size from 320×160 to 1000. To minimize the time spent loading the encoded Google Earth reference images, all image vectors were stacked into a $1000 \times N$ -dimensional matrix and loaded onto the GPU. Then, based on a prediction of the current live image pose, the matrix was indexed to include only the reference images that are 4 meters ahead and behind along the path. Using this method, they achieved results comparable to previous approaches while significantly reducing memory and computational cost.

The core method of *Autoencoder Satellite Image Matching for UAV Geolocation in Long-Range High-Altitude Missions* [17] also relies on a convolutional autoencoder trained on RGB satellite images from Google Earth. Images were clipped into 320×160 pixel tiles over a large area in Brazil, forming a reference map of 2022 and a query map of 2023 images to test robustness. The encoder compresses each input image into a 1000-dimensional latent vector, while the decoder reconstructs the image, aiding training but unused during inference. The loss function combines photometric reconstruction loss (mean squared error) and intermediate layer matching losses from five layers, weighted by $\alpha = 0.01$, ensuring that the network retains semantically informative latent representations. The model was trained using PyTorch in 200 epochs. During inference, each query image is encoded and matched to

Figure 4: The model used in [1].

the most similar pre-encoded reference embedding using normalized cross-correlation ($r_{\bar{x},\bar{y}} = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \bar{x}_i \bar{y}_i$). This method is accurate and efficient, performing a matching in 0.05ms. Matching was performed by matrix-vector multiplication between the 1000-dimensional query embedding and a matrix of reference embeddings. The authors evaluated the model across ten map sizes, covering areas up to 41,287.68 km². The optimal configuration (Map 5: 20,643.84 km²) achieved 96.83% accuracy along a 200 km path of sequential UAV images in known terrain, and an average 90% accuracy across eight different unknown paths, which means significantly better performance compared to classical methods such as SIFT (79.37%), ORB (47.62%), and BRIEF (6.35%). The proposed approach proved robust to appearance changes across years, generalizable to unseen regions, and scalable for large-area UAV navigation. The authors emphasize its potential integration with aircraft flight models (e.g., particle filters) for real-time UAV localization.

Another approach to UAV localization is demonstrated in *Season-Invariant GNSS-Denied Visual Localization for UAVs* by Kinnari, Verdoja and Kyrki [2]. They approached the problem differently because if the model were trained only on satellite images, it would not have been so successful for drone images taken at different times of day or in different seasons. That is why they used a Siamese network, which is trained on image pairs and has to learn whether they are similar or not. Their model turned out to be invariant to significant seasonal appearance differences (winter-summer) between the camera image and the map. Their results showed significant improvements over conventional reference methods, especially under high seasonal variation, highlighting the model’s effectiveness for real-world, all-season UAV localization tasks.

The paper titled *A Practical Cross-View Image Matching Method between UAV and Satellite for UAV-Based Geo-Localization* [18] introduces a Location Classification Method (LCM) for cross-view image matching between UAV and satellite images. The primary objective is to enhance UAV-based geo-localization and navigation by accurately matching images from these two different viewpoints. It uses the University-1652 dataset, which includes both UAV and satellite images of 1,652 buildings from 72 universities around the world. Due to challenges in obtaining real UAV images for all buildings, synthetic UAV images were generated using Google Earth’s 3D models. The LCM approach treats each building (location) as a distinct class, enabling the model to learn discriminative features for each location by classifying images from both UAV and satellite views into the same category. The input images are resized to 384 × 384 pixels. The network they used as the LCM’s baseline model is set as follows: ResNet-50 [19] is used as the backbone network; the output dimension of the fully connected layer size is set to 512; the new classification layer is added after the fully connected layer. Cross-entropy loss was used for training. Dur-

ing the testing phase, the classification layer was removed, and the 512-dimensional features were extracted for both UAV (A) and satellite (B) images. Cosine similarity (CS) is used to measure the correlation between the features of image A and the features of image B. The larger the CS, the smaller the distance between the two features and greater the correlation between the corresponding images:

$$\text{CS} = \cos(\theta) = \frac{\mathbf{f}_A \cdot \mathbf{f}_B}{\|\mathbf{f}_A\| \times \|\mathbf{f}_B\|} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n f_{Ai} f_{Bi}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (f_{Ai}^2)} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (f_{Bi}^2)}}, \quad (16)$$

where f_A and f_B are the feature vectors of images A and B; f_{Ai} and f_{Bi} are the components of the feature vectors. The LCM method was compared to a previous model by Zheng et al [20]. The results indicate that LCM outperforms the previous model in Recall@1 (the proportion of correct matches within the top 1 retrieved result), Recall@10 and average precision metrics. Overall, the LCM can more effectively extract the image features of the two views, thereby improving the matching accuracy. In addition, the Recall@1 and average precision in UAV-to-satellite are more significantly improved than satellite-to-UAV.

The authors of *GPS-Denied UAV Localization using Pre-existing Satellite Imagery* [21] proposed a method requiring only a downward-facing monocular RGB camera on the UAV, and pre-existing satellite imagery of the flight location to which the UAV imagery is compared and aligned. To overcome differences in the image capturing conditions between the satellite and UAV, such as seasonal and perspective changes, they used Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) representations trained on readily available satellite data. They used a model that contains two fully-convolutional neural networks in parallel with shared weights, through which the images to be aligned are passed. After the convolutional network, the feature images are passed into a differentiable implementation of the Inverse Compositional Lucas-Kanade (ICLK) algorithm [22]. Loss functions are designed in order to learn the weights of the convolutional layers, so that the feature images passed to the ICLK layer are as photometrically similar as possible. For a GPS-denied flight at 200m altitude, over a flight distance of 850m, they achieved an average localization error of less than 8 meters.

The paper *Efficient UAV localization using combined autoencoder and SIFT* [23] introduces a vision-based localization method combining autoencoder and SIFT algorithms. This approach compresses high-resolution map images into low-dimensional vectors, which are stored in a database for efficient retrieval. During localization, UAV images are encoded and matched with the database, followed by SIFT and homography projection for precise positioning. The AE+SIFT approach makes the localization more precise, achieving an average error of 3.94 meters relative to the ground truth. The authors highlight that when UAV images are misaligned with

reference images (that is, in the case of satellite images), their method outperforms the existing AE method in terms of accuracy.

The paper *Real-time Geo-localization Using Satellite Imagery and Topography for Unmanned Aerial Vehicles* [24] presents a method that stores the descriptors of the satellite images from Google Earth. There are a variety of choices of whole-image descriptors and compressed representations of images. NetVLAD [25] is used in this case as the global descriptor because it is easily accessible in almost all deep learning frameworks. They use a modified version of it to combine the features extracted by MobileNet [26] with a NetVLAD layer. In this representation, each global descriptor is a 1-by-4096 row vector that is loaded into the UAV’s memory. SuperPoint [27] is applied as the local descriptor choice. Unlike hand-crafted descriptors such as SIFT, whose number of detected key points can vary, NN-based descriptors trigger a fixed amount of computation from end to end, while also being more robust to scene changes. Instead of matching the descriptors using the brute-force matcher, which iterates over all elements in the two sets without understanding the semantic content, SuperGlue [28] is used to find the correspondences between the local descriptors of two images. They calculated with a 640×480 image size. First, they calculated using a global descriptor for the query image captured from the UAV camera. They computed the l^2 -norm of the differences between the global descriptor of the query image and every global descriptor in the prepared array and sorted them in ascending order. After that, local descriptors were inferred for the query image and matched with the top n candidates in the sorted list using SuperGlue. The number n was determined by the trade-off between performance and accuracy. This method resulted in an RMSE value of less than 3 meters.

The article *A Review on Deep Learning for UAV Absolute Visual Localization* [29] gives an extensive review of different approaches for the UAV localization problem. It mentions the complexity of image matching in real-world scenarios where UAV views are often compared with imagery from different sources, such as satellites, reconnaissance aircraft, or other UAVs specialized in mapping, reconnaissance, and photogrammetry. Matching images from different airborne sensors introduces another layer of difficulty because variations in sensor size, resolution, dynamic range, noise, and noise profiles can have a negative influence on the matching accuracy. The most recent approaches use CNN and Vision Transformer (ViT) architectures to solve the problem of matching satellite and UAV images. These types of models are effective in finding and matching image features because they can learn hierarchical representations directly from raw image data. CNNs are very good at detecting and recognizing features such as edges, textures, and patterns at different levels of abstraction, making them robust against variations in lighting, angles, and noise. Attention mechanisms make ViT architectures even more effective in feature detec-

tion, allowing the model to focus on specific parts of an image that are most relevant to the task. Its overview of localization methods involves some approaches that use Euclidean and others that use cosine distance or custom similarity measures.

Based on the above results, I selected autoencoder models to represent images as low-dimensional vectors. My goal is to learn vector representations such that corresponding UAV and satellite images are positioned close to each other in the latent space. In previous studies, metrics such as Euclidean distance, cosine similarity, or cross-correlation were used to compare image pairs. In some cases, simply encoding the images into a latent space using an autoencoder was sufficient to ensure that similar images were mapped closely together. However, other approaches incorporated additional models—such as GANs or SIFT—to better align UAV and satellite imagery.

In my approach, I first used autoencoders trained solely on satellite images, without applying any image-matching techniques. I also experimented with a CycleGAN model to align UAV and satellite images before embedding them into the latent space and computing their distances. Some studies employed symmetric models trained from scratch, while others used pre-trained networks like ResNet or MobileNet, which are known for their strong feature extraction capabilities. I chose to train my models on RGB images, as they capture more information than grayscale images.

4 Data

The data I used for my research was provided by the Systems and Control Laboratory of HUN-REN SZTAKI, containing images taken by a drone camera near Mórahalom with associated sensor data. The images have RGB channels and relatively good resolution. The sensor data contains the latitude, longitude and above sea level altitude for every picture taken during the flight as well as the roll, pitch and yaw values as it is shown in Figure 5. Yaw means a rotation around the z-axis, pitch around the y-axis, roll around the x-axis. The yaw, pitch, and roll rotations can be used to place a 3D body in any orientation [30]. The altitude fluctuated between 350 and 385 meters. The coordinates of the investigated area are between the edges listed in Table 1.

Figure 5: Sensor data of the drone flight.

To train the models, I used satellite images from Google Earth that I received in a geotiff file storing the coordinates in addition to the RGB values of each pixel. Some examples of drone and satellite image pairs are shown in Figure 6. Due to different shades of colors, it is challenging for models trained on satellite images to recognize drone images. Another difficulty is that we examine a quite homogeneous area consisting largely of forests.

After generating the training coordinates, I cropped the images with those center coordinates from this geotiff file to a certain size. In this way, I had as many training images as needed with overlapping so that the models could be trained on the whole area.

Edge	Longitude	Latitude
Upper Left	19.730522	46.190865
Lower Left	19.730522	46.144606
Upper Right	19.763066	46.190865
Lower Right	19.763066	46.144606

Table 1: The edge coordinates of the geotiff file.

Figure 6: Example drone and satellite image pairs.

Most calculations needed to be done in meters instead of the latitude-longitude coordinate system (e.g. the deviation from the correct value should be measured in meters), so I had to convert the values into a meter-based system. According to the epsg.io website, the HD72/EOV system with EPSG:23700 code [31] is suitable, since it is meter-based and covers the whole area of Hungary, see Figure 7.

Figure 7: The area covered by the HD72 coordinate system. Source: [31]

4.1 Data preparation

As shown in Figure 5, the heading of the pictures taken by the drone is not fixed, but changing as the drone is turning. In order to align the heading of the pictures with the satellite images, I had to rotate them by the yaw angle multiplied by -1, as the satellite images have a fixed heading of North. The drone was tilted when turning, and did not capture the image right below it, which would be misleading when training models, so I filtered out the images with roll value larger than 7.5° (I chose this threshold manually by looking at the data). I used the middle 3600×3600 pixels of these images and resized as required by the models. In the satellite images, 1 pixel distance corresponds to roughly 0.2 meters.

To handle the GeoTIFF format of the satellite image, I used the rasterio Python package and needed to find the optimal zoom to have the satellite images in the same size as the drone images [32].

5 Methods

In this section, I explain the data pipeline I developed for the experiment. First, I generated training coordinates containing the locations of every camera image and the 200-meter neighborhood grid of these points by 5-meter steps, filtering out the coordinates that fell outside the boundaries of the satellite image. It resulted in more than 285,000 coordinates, of which I used 80% for training and 20% for validation. I cropped out parts of the satellite image around these coordinates as center points and trained the autoencoder models on these cutouts.

For the evaluation, at each photo taken by the drone, we need to search for the satellite image cutout that is the most similar to the photo taken. This satellite image cutout will be near the real position of the drone, so I used a 10m by 10m neighborhood grid around each image to select candidates for evaluating against the drone’s photo. After encoding and saving the satellite images corresponding to each coordinate of the grid, I then encoded the drone images individually. For each drone image, the latent vector was compared to the surrounding satellite image vectors using a chosen distance metric (cosine distance or normalized cross-correlation). The satellite image with the most similar latent representation was considered the best match. Then I calculated model performance measures.

5.1 Models

5.1.1 Convolutional autoencoder

I used symmetric convolutional autoencoder from scratch, very similar to the Bianchi-Barfoot model [1] shown in Figure 1. I modified the linear and batch normalization layers, and used inputs with 3 channels instead of grayscale images. I cropped the center 3600×3600 pixels of the UAV and satellite images and resized to 640×640 . The dimension of the latent space is 3200.

To have meaningful latent vectors, I decided to try out pre-trained convolutional neural networks, which have already proven to be good in feature extraction. I used the pre-trained VGG16 [33], EfficientNet-B0 [34] and ResNet50 [19] models to capture the important characteristics of the images into encoded vectors in the latent space. I added a convolutional bottleneck layer with a certain dimension (128, 64, or 32). A bottleneck size of 128 corresponds to a latent space dimension of 6,272; a size of 64 results in a dimension of 3,136; and a size of 32 yields a dimension of 1,568. To reconstruct the images from the vectors, I used a decoder containing five convolutional layers with upsampling layers and ReLU activation functions between them. I compared these three model types with the three different bottleneck dimensions resulting in nine models with pre-trained encoders. I used a

learning rate of 0.001, MSE loss and Adam optimizer in all cases and trained the models for 5 epochs on images in RGB format, because it contains more information than grayscale format. These models require image size 224×224 , so I resized the initially cropped 3600×3600 pixels to 224×224 . With these dimensions, the bottleneck sizes of 128, 64 and 32 mean a data reduction to 0.048%, 0.024%, and 0.012% of the original sizes, respectively.

All model trainings were conducted using the PyTorch deep learning framework on a high-performance server equipped with $2 \times$ AMD EPYC 7F72 @ 3.2 GHz 24-core CPUs (48 physical cores, 96 logical threads), approximately 1 TB of RAM, 10 TB of SSD storage, and $8 \times$ NVIDIA A100 GPUs with 40 GB memory each. This setup allowed for efficient parallel processing and high-throughput training of multiple model configurations.

5.1.2 CycleGAN to align UAV and satellite images

As it can be seen in Figure 6, the hue, contrast and brightness of the UAV and satellite images are quite different and the drone images were captured at a different time of day (much longer shadows) and perhaps in a different season as well (the color of the forest). This differences can cause bias in finding the nearest satellite images, even if the models were trained to create meaningful encoded vectors and find similar satellite images.

CycleGAN models were used in the scientific literature by other researchers, and they turned out to be a good tool to align UAV and satellite images. I used the online available tutorial from the webpage of Tensorflow [35], and tried it using different learning rates. I had the best results when training it for 15 epochs with a learning rate of 5. I applied this model to the drone images before computing the encoded vectors and comparing them to the nearby satellite images.

I evaluated all models with and without applying the CycleGAN model, and compared the results.

5.2 Evaluation

To be able to evaluate the model performance, a distance metric is needed first between the encoded satellite and drone image vectors in the latent space. Instead of Euclidean distance, cosine distance and normalized cross-correlation proved to be more accurate in terms of prediction performance. Recall that cosine distance is defined as $1 - \text{cosine similarity}$, see eq. (16). When using these latter metrics, vectors corresponding to visually similar images were positioned closer in the latent space compared to when Euclidean distance was used.

In addition to the camera images, a prediction can be calculated using the sensor data every moment (with a certain error, so the images need to be used), so it can be enough to compare the drone images to the satellite images near them. The calculations were made along grids with 10-meter step size in 100, 200 and 500-meter neighborhoods of the camera images.

Figure 8: The drone path, the grid coordinates and the edges of the geotiff file shown in one image.

To measure how much distance there is in meters between the true and predicted locations, I used the RMSE (root mean square error) and MAE (mean absolute error) values:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2},$$

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |\hat{y}_i - y_i|,$$

where the \hat{y}_i are the predicted and the y_i are the true values.

For further evaluation, I calculated the top $p\%$ accuracy for several values of p . This quantity shows that according to a model, what proportion of the test data has the true value among the top $p\%$ predictions (whether the encoded vector of the nearest satellite image is included in the top $p\%$ closest vectors according to the cosine distance/cross-correlation). In multiclass classifications, this can be a better measure than top-one accuracy, because in some cases, the top-one prediction of the models is incorrect, but the ground truth comes directly after it. It may have the same top 1 accuracy as other models, but it associates the true class with a much higher prediction probability.

In addition, I calculated the NDCG values of the models. NDCG (Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain) is a popular evaluation metric used in information

retrieval, ranking systems, and machine learning to measure the effectiveness of ranking algorithms. It measures how well a model ranks relevant items compared to an ideal ranking [36].

DCG (Discounted Cumulative Gain) quantifies the usefulness (or relevance) of results while considering the order in which they are presented. It applies a discount factor to account for the position of relevant items in the ranked list. The idea is that highly relevant documents appearing earlier in the ranking should contribute more to the score.

$$DCG@k = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{rel_i}{\log_2(i+1)},$$

where rel_i is the relevance score of the item at position i and $\log_2(i+1)$ is the discount factor that penalizes lower-ranked items.

To normalize DCG, we compute IDCG, which is the DCG score if items were ranked in optimal order (i.e. sorted by highest relevance first). NDCG normalizes DCG by dividing it by the ideal DCG:

$$NDCG@k = \frac{DCG@k}{IDCG@k}.$$

NDCG ranges from 0 to 1, with 1 being the best possible ranking. When evaluating my models, I calculated NDCG with $k = 15$, because it seemed to make the most difference between the models.

All models were evaluated by identifying the nearest latent vector based on both cosine similarity and cross-correlation. In addition, I selected the two best-performing models in both cases and used the average of their calculated distances in the latent space to determine the prediction, because the combination of different models can often lead to better accuracy [4].

6 Results

Figure 9 shows four example satellite images autoencoded by the models to illustrate how they managed to reconstruct the original images from the latent vectors. To the human eye, the from-scratch autoencoder produces the most similar reconstruction to the original image, with only slight blurring. The more complex pre-trained models work differently. They recognize the borders of the different patterns on the images as features, making them sharper and blurring everything else. I visualized three different models with a bottleneck size of 128 stacked vertically for comparison. There are no major differences between the VGG16 and the EfficientNet-B0 models, but the reconstructions of ResNet50 are less clear than the other two. I also compared the same model (VGG16) with different bottleneck sizes, and the reconstructed images appear visibly blurrier as the latent dimension gets smaller.

I also visualized the results of the CycleGAN generating satellite-like images from UAV data. Figure 10 shows the original UAV, the GAN-generated satellite-like, and the original satellite images of the same coordinates for the same four example images as before. The model succeeded in changing the colors to better match. However, the landscape has changed since the two sets of images were captured, and the drone sensors have a few meters deviation from the satellite positions, which cannot be fully corrected by CycleGAN alone.

Figure 9: Reconstructed satellite images by 6 different models: a symmetric from-scratch convolutional autoencoder, an EfficientNet-B0 and ResNet50-based model with 128 bottleneck dimension, and three VGG16-based models with bottleneck sizes of 128, 64 and 32.

Figure 10: The original UAV, the GAN-generated UAV and the satellite images of the same coordinates.

I evaluated all models, identifying the top 1 prediction using both cosine similarity and cross-correlation of the latent vector representations, since this metric significantly affects prediction accuracy. I then selected the two best-performing models under both cosine distance and cross-correlation evaluations. To construct an ensemble prediction, I averaged their respective distance scores for each input and selected the satellite image with the lowest resulting value.

I calculated the MAE and RMSE values of the models evaluated both with and without applying CycleGAN. Tables 2, 3, and 4 show the results for radii of 500,

200 and 100 meters, respectively. When using cosine similarity, the VGG16-based models achieved the best scores, although the errors are higher than expected, with the VGG16 model with 128 bottleneck size without CycleGAN being the one with the lowest error. At the 500m range, it achieved an MAE of 151.61m and an RMSE of 222.88m; at 200m radius, the MAE was 61.76m, the RMSE was 83.51m, while in 100m the MAE and RMSE values were 44.17m and 51.14m, respectively. When evaluating the localization at a radius of 100m, applying the CycleGAN model improved performance in almost all cases. At the 200 and 500m evaluation ranges, VGG16-based models performed better without using CycleGAN, while all other models showed improved performance with it. The second-best model here was the Resnet50-based model with CycleGAN, so I used the combination of these two models as an ensemble model. This newly introduced model turned out to be the best performing one with MAE 109.73m and RMSE 179.21m at 500m evaluation radius, MAE 49.66m and RMSE 70.02m at 200m radius, and MAE 36.93m and RMSE 42.92m at 100m radius.

When evaluating using cross-correlation, the pre-trained models show no major differences compared to previous results. For some of them, it slightly improved the MAE and RMSE values; for others, the errors increased slightly. Again, applying CycleGAN improved predictions for all models except VGG16. The from-scratch symmetric autoencoder shows here the most notable and unexpected improvement. With CycleGAN, it achieved an MAE of 139.53m and an RMSE of 212.12m at the 500m evaluation radius, 57.99m MAE and 84.21m RMSE at 200m radius, and 33.31m MAE and 39.62m RMSE at a radius of 100m. These results make it the best model in all evaluation radii, excluding ensemble models. The second-best was VGG16 with a bottleneck size of 128, evaluated without CycleGAN. These two models were combined to form an ensemble, which achieved an MAE of 97.8m, 45.33m and 31.78m at evaluation radii of 500m, 200m and 100m, while having a RMSE of 167.14m, 65.86m and 36.85m at radii of 500m, 200m and 100m, respectively.

To better understand model performance, it is useful to examine the full distribution rather than just the mean values. Figure 11 shows the kernel density estimates of the top 1 prediction error for the three evaluation radii, using both cosine similarity and cross-correlation. The diagrams on the left correspond to evaluations based on cosine similarity, while those on the right correspond to cross-correlation. The first and third columns contain the results I computed without using CycleGAN, and the second and fourth columns consist of the error distributions after applying CycleGAN.

When considering cosine similarity, the density curves in the “With GAN” column shift leftward compared to those in the “Without GAN” column across all three evaluation radii for most models. This leftward shift indicates smaller pre-

diction errors on average after applying CycleGAN. VGG16 with a bottleneck size of 128 is undoubtedly the best-performing model showing the sharpest and left-most peaks; it has large prediction errors occurring in only a small number of cases. ResNet50 and EfficientNet models show moderate performance, with ResNet50, especially with a bottleneck size of 128, outperforming EfficientNet when CycleGAN is applied. The from-scratch autoencoder performs the worst, with much broader and more right-shifted error distributions. Across all architectures, increasing the embedding dimensionality from 32 to 64 to 128 tends to improve performance, as indicated by progressively sharper and more left-shifted curves. The ensemble model has the highest peak and places minimal weight on larger errors.

In the cross-correlation-based plots, the curves belonging to the pre-trained models closely resemble those in the cosine similarity plots. However, in the GAN column, the purple line—representing the from-scratch model—rises above the others at low error values. The ensemble model in this setting has an even higher peak around 30m error and assigns even less weight to larger errors than the other ensemble model belonging to cosine similarity.

So far, only the top 1 prediction was evaluated. However, considering the top k predictions for a larger values of k can provide deeper insights into model performance. I used NDCG and top $p\%$ accuracy as additional evaluation metrics. Tables 2, 3, 4 show the NDCG, top 1%, 5% and 10% accuracy values for the models with and without the application of CycleGAN.

As the evaluation radius increases, the NDCG values also improve. At 500m, most scores exceed 0.7 with the ensemble model on VGG and ResNet with CycleGAN having the highest value of 0.8961. Among individual models, EfficientNet with a bottleneck size of 128 using CycleGAN and cross-correlation has the top performance in terms of NDCG with 0.8592. This indicates that although it is not the best in finding the nearest satellite image, it usually assigns the 15 smallest latent distances to images that are close to the ground truth. At the radius of 200m, the best-performing ensemble and individual models are the same, with NDCG values of 0.8547 and 0.8263, respectively. At 100m as well, the EfficientNet model with a bottleneck size of 128 with CycleGAN and cross-correlation has the highest value with 0.7577 among non-ensemble methods, while the combination of VGG with a bottleneck dimension of 128 and the from-scratch model with GAN has the overall best performance in terms of NDCG with 0.7735.

Similar to NDCG, top- $p\%$ accuracy decreases as the evaluation radius becomes smaller. According to the Table 2, at 500m radius, the from-scratch autoencoder using cross-correlation and CycleGAN achieves the best scores among individual models with 0.5913, 0.6310 and 0.6429 for p values of 1, 5 and 10. In contrast, the same model using cosine similarity without GAN has the lowest accuracy values.

The overall best performance belongs to the cross-correlation ensemble model with 0.7302, 0.7639 and 0.7778 for the top-1%, 5% and 10% accuracy. This indicates that for 73% of the test data, it has the closest satellite image among the top 1% predictions. At an evaluation radius of 200m, the from-scratch autoencoder turned out to have the best score in terms of top-1% accuracy with 0.1925, but considering the top 5% and 10% accuracy, the cross-correlation ensemble model is better with 0.7956 and 0.8571. At 100m radius, VGG16 with a 128-dimensional bottleneck with GAN using cosine similarity is the overall best-performing model in terms of top 1% accuracy with 0.0615, while the from-scratch autoencoder has the highest values of top-5% and 10% accuracy with 0.2877 and 0.6310. EfficientNet and ResNet models have moderate performance, with ResNet being slightly better.

Figure 12 shows the top-p% accuracy curves as a function of p for all models. For example, at p=10, the curve shows the proportion of test cases in which the grid point closest to the ground truth location appears among the top 10% most similar candidates. In this evaluation, a larger area under the curve corresponds to better performance. Across all radii, the “With GAN” column consistently shows higher and tighter curves for all models except VGG, especially at lower p values, which are the most important in real scenarios. The diagram also demonstrates that higher-dimensional embeddings produce better top-p curves.

In the cosine distance plots, VGG16 with a bottleneck dimension of 128 is the best-performing model when CycleGAN is not applied. This evaluation metric differentiates the performance of the different model types, with the three VGG models being the best, followed by the three EfficientNet models, and the ResNet models being the least effective. Using CycleGAN modifies this ranking by improving the accuracy of ResNet models allowing them to catch up to the VGG models. Across all cases using cosine distance, the from-scratch model performs the worst of all.

In the cross-correlation-based evaluation without CycleGAN, pre-trained models perform similarly to their performance under cosine distance, while the curve corresponding to the from-scratch model is significantly higher than with cosine distance. The usage of CycleGAN makes the same differences in the case of pre-trained models as in the cosine distance part, improving the accuracy of all of them except VGG. The most surprising difference is that the from-scratch model outperforms all other individual models under this metric.

The ensemble models outperform all individual models across all radii in both the cosine distance and the cross-correlation parts, with the cross-correlation ensemble model, i.e., the combination of the VGG model with a bottleneck size of 128 without GAN and the from-scratch model with GAN being slightly better than the cosine distance-based ensemble.

Model	MAE	RMSE	NDCG	1% ACC	5% ACC	10% ACC
From-scratch AE	357.66	386.75	0.5798	0.0794	0.1032	0.1310
From-scratch AE, cc	305.73	347.03	0.7127	0.1548	0.1944	0.2202
From-scratch AE, GAN	294.86	342.18	0.7050	0.2103	0.2401	0.2738
From-scratch AE, GAN, cc	139.53	212.12	0.7889	0.5913	0.6310	0.6429
EfficientNet 32dim	263.16	315.63	0.7646	0.2341	0.3016	0.3313
EfficientNet 32dim, cc	266.37	318.72	0.7526	0.2262	0.2917	0.3353
EfficientNet 32dim, GAN	237.60	294.48	0.8115	0.2639	0.3651	0.4028
EfficientNet 32dim, GAN, cc	232.99	292.65	0.8298	0.2956	0.3849	0.4087
EfficientNet 64dim	251.04	304.44	0.7718	0.2579	0.3175	0.3472
EfficientNet 64dim, cc	256.14	310.80	0.7693	0.2540	0.3214	0.3532
EfficientNet 64dim, GAN	251.40	304.43	0.7925	0.2361	0.3155	0.3591
EfficientNet 64dim, GAN, cc	223.98	284.73	0.8379	0.3254	0.4028	0.4444
EfficientNet 128dim	242.83	298.68	0.7771	0.2798	0.3433	0.3790
EfficientNet 128dim, cc	236.04	295.98	0.7984	0.3135	0.3730	0.4107
EfficientNet 128dim, GAN	249.76	299.79	0.7832	0.2242	0.2996	0.3552
EfficientNet 128dim, GAN, cc	205.67	266.52	0.8592	0.3492	0.4405	0.4782
ResNet50 32dim	316.49	357.62	0.6710	0.1627	0.2004	0.2242
ResNet50 32dim, cc	320.56	360.64	0.6628	0.1587	0.1944	0.2103
ResNet50 32dim, GAN	218.60	280.59	0.8079	0.3294	0.4127	0.4524
ResNet50 32dim, GAN, cc	215.33	276.70	0.8073	0.3294	0.4206	0.4544
ResNet50 64dim	289.30	333.46	0.7720	0.1925	0.2282	0.2540
ResNet50 64dim, cc	302.53	342.98	0.7521	0.1647	0.1984	0.2222
ResNet50 64dim, GAN	207.74	268.39	0.8087	0.3552	0.4325	0.4782
ResNet50 64dim, GAN, cc	203.05	265.36	0.8145	0.3730	0.4444	0.4960
ResNet50 128dim	305.03	349.14	0.7581	0.1845	0.2282	0.2560
ResNet50 128dim, cc	316.11	357.50	0.7440	0.1687	0.2063	0.2321
ResNet50 128dim, GAN	197.74	264.21	0.8463	0.4008	0.4742	0.5119
ResNet50 128dim, GAN, cc	197.57	264.58	0.8528	0.4028	0.4821	0.5159
VGG16 32dim	204.64	267.54	0.7961	0.3710	0.4385	0.4782
VGG16 32dim, cc	204.79	268.12	0.7914	0.3690	0.4464	0.4821
VGG16 32dim, GAN	222.66	281.34	0.7518	0.3214	0.3909	0.4306
VGG16 32dim, GAN, cc	207.82	269.59	0.7741	0.3671	0.4306	0.4683
VGG16 64dim	171.29	240.27	0.8214	0.4702	0.5417	0.5794
VGG16 64dim, cc	182.63	250.92	0.7984	0.4444	0.5139	0.5516
VGG16 64dim, GAN	198.64	261.35	0.7787	0.3909	0.4504	0.4881
VGG16 64dim, GAN, cc	188.70	256.64	0.8008	0.4365	0.4960	0.5298
VGG16 128dim	151.61	222.88	0.8488	0.5377	0.6071	0.6290
VGG16 128dim, cc	159.89	231.70	0.8480	0.5278	0.5873	0.6071
VGG16 128dim, GAN	190.70	255.23	0.7855	0.4028	0.4643	0.5179
VGG16 128dim, GAN, cc	170.67	236.82	0.8195	0.4563	0.5258	0.5675
VGG(128)+ResNet(128), GAN	109.73	179.21	0.8961	0.6825	0.7262	0.7500
VGG(128)+From-scratch, GAN, cc	97.80	167.14	0.8674	0.7302	0.7639	0.7778

Table 2: Performance metrics for models with and without GAN, evaluated in 500m radius. Cc stands for cross-correlation, and the others were calculated with cosine similarity.

Model	MAE	RMSE	NDCG	1% ACC	5% ACC	10% ACC
From-scratch AE	145.78	159.32	0.6045	0.0377	0.1647	0.1865
From-scratch AE, cc	103.57	127.25	0.7115	0.1111	0.4087	0.4464
From-scratch AE, GAN	103.94	127.66	0.7033	0.0873	0.4107	0.4563
From-scratch AE, GAN, cc	57.99	84.21	0.7707	0.1925	0.7183	0.7659
EffNet 32 dim	103.15	121.92	0.7282	0.0496	0.2956	0.3929
EffNet 32 dim, cc	103.19	122.08	0.7262	0.0496	0.2937	0.3988
EffNet 32 dim, GAN	89.13	109.77	0.7795	0.0813	0.4008	0.4782
EffNet 32 dim, GAN, cc	84.56	105.78	0.7952	0.0913	0.4405	0.5238
EffNet 64 dim	99.82	120.44	0.7352	0.0754	0.3552	0.4345
EffNet 64 dim, cc	97.60	118.10	0.7414	0.0714	0.3591	0.4524
EffNet 64 dim, GAN	92.86	113.54	0.7739	0.0635	0.3948	0.4643
EffNet 64 dim, GAN, cc	82.04	103.38	0.8067	0.0754	0.4643	0.5417
EffNet 128 dim	96.53	117.44	0.7556	0.0635	0.3770	0.4623
EffNet 128 dim, cc	88.71	109.99	0.7797	0.0714	0.4306	0.5179
EffNet 128 dim, GAN	94.36	114.07	0.7686	0.0694	0.3750	0.4464
EffNet 128 dim, GAN, cc	78.15	99.03	0.8263	0.1111	0.4762	0.5536
ResNet50 32 dim	118.69	137.53	0.6923	0.0615	0.2758	0.3393
ResNet50 32 dim, cc	120.54	139.11	0.6871	0.0575	0.2659	0.3254
ResNet50 32 dim, GAN	89.11	111.24	0.7778	0.0933	0.4286	0.5119
ResNet50 32 dim, GAN, cc	87.70	109.94	0.7791	0.0992	0.4405	0.5179
ResNet50 64 dim	103.21	123.34	0.7516	0.0952	0.3333	0.4048
ResNet50 64 dim, cc	108.42	128.18	0.7432	0.0952	0.3095	0.3770
ResNet50 64 dim, GAN	84.65	106.63	0.7793	0.0813	0.4603	0.5417
ResNet50 64 dim, GAN, cc	83.75	106.23	0.7831	0.0893	0.4663	0.5516
ResNet50 128 dim	102.92	123.02	0.7468	0.0694	0.3492	0.4127
ResNet50 128 dim, cc	106.49	126.41	0.7404	0.0655	0.3353	0.3929
ResNet50 128 dim, GAN	73.65	96.12	0.8156	0.1210	0.5198	0.6389
ResNet50 128 dim, GAN, cc	74.54	96.74	0.8195	0.1151	0.5099	0.6270
VGG16 32 dim	76.47	98.87	0.7568	0.1052	0.5238	0.6012
VGG16 32 dim, cc	77.51	100.29	0.7568	0.1032	0.5278	0.6032
VGG16 32 dim, GAN	79.74	102.03	0.7420	0.1329	0.4762	0.5615
VGG16 32 dim, GAN, cc	77.98	101.01	0.7576	0.1468	0.5119	0.5853
VGG16 64 dim	68.90	90.55	0.7795	0.1151	0.5833	0.6488
VGG16 64 dim, cc	72.28	94.36	0.7685	0.1131	0.5556	0.6270
VGG16 64 dim, GAN	74.12	97.36	0.7607	0.1210	0.5476	0.6230
VGG16 64 dim, GAN, cc	72.16	95.85	0.7764	0.1270	0.5714	0.6369
VGG16 128 dim	61.76	83.51	0.8040	0.1389	0.6389	0.7083
VGG16 128 dim, cc	62.63	85.20	0.8068	0.1349	0.6369	0.7123
VGG16 128 dim, GAN	71.11	94.59	0.7707	0.1488	0.5635	0.6230
VGG16 128 dim, GAN, cc	65.77	88.50	0.7947	0.1429	0.6052	0.6706
VGG(128)+ResNet(128), GAN	49.66	70.02	0.8547	0.1647	0.7679	0.8254
VGG(128)+From-scratch, GAN, cc	45.33	65.86	0.8363	0.1806	0.7956	0.8571

Table 3: Performance metrics for models with and without GAN, evaluated in 200m radius. Cc stands for cross-correlation, and the others were calculated with cosine similarity.

Model	MAE	RMSE	NDCG	1% ACC	5% ACC	10% ACC
From-scratch AE	70.66	77.70	0.6100	0.0218	0.1151	0.2222
From-scratch AE, cc	46.08	55.30	0.6842	0.0357	0.2163	0.4782
From-scratch AE, GAN	50.34	59.45	0.6837	0.0298	0.1825	0.4167
From-scratch AE, GAN, cc	33.31	39.62	0.7232	0.0397	0.2877	0.6310
EffNet 32 dim	55.92	62.27	0.6767	0.0218	0.0913	0.2460
EffNet 32 dim, cc	54.98	61.44	0.6771	0.0238	0.0992	0.2599
EffNet 32 dim, GAN	47.64	54.54	0.7220	0.0317	0.1429	0.3611
EffNet 32 dim, GAN, cc	46.54	53.36	0.7318	0.0298	0.1448	0.3611
EffNet 64 dim	50.88	57.87	0.6835	0.0119	0.1409	0.3214
EffNet 64 dim, cc	51.16	58.11	0.6876	0.0198	0.1369	0.3056
EffNet 64 dim, GAN	49.78	56.83	0.7238	0.0238	0.1389	0.3393
EffNet 64 dim, GAN, cc	46.12	53.13	0.7430	0.0278	0.1647	0.3790
EffNet 128 dim	50.74	57.34	0.7071	0.0198	0.1151	0.3016
EffNet 128 dim, cc	48.25	54.91	0.7244	0.0179	0.1230	0.3254
EffNet 128 dim, GAN	50.89	58.08	0.7210	0.0317	0.1488	0.3175
EffNet 128 dim, GAN, cc	44.53	51.34	0.7577	0.0278	0.1865	0.3929
ResNet50 32 dim	56.92	64.09	0.6692	0.0198	0.1171	0.2540
ResNet50 32 dim, cc	58.43	65.51	0.6671	0.0179	0.1071	0.2440
ResNet50 32 dim, GAN	48.13	55.37	0.7211	0.0218	0.1548	0.3532
ResNet50 32 dim, GAN, cc	47.88	55.17	0.7231	0.0238	0.1627	0.3512
ResNet50 64 dim	48.96	56.32	0.7010	0.0218	0.1687	0.3591
ResNet50 64 dim, cc	49.42	56.90	0.6984	0.0238	0.1687	0.3552
ResNet50 64 dim, GAN	46.81	54.36	0.7210	0.0258	0.1607	0.3770
ResNet50 64 dim, GAN, cc	46.44	53.95	0.7238	0.0258	0.1647	0.3810
ResNet50 128 dim	49.81	57.05	0.6992	0.0139	0.1567	0.3552
ResNet50 128 dim, cc	49.54	56.80	0.6975	0.0139	0.1607	0.3611
ResNet50 128 dim, GAN	42.13	48.61	0.7465	0.0159	0.1964	0.4147
ResNet50 128 dim, GAN, cc	42.38	48.95	0.7494	0.0179	0.1964	0.4087
VGG16 32 dim	44.17	51.14	0.7024	0.0278	0.1647	0.4067
VGG16 32 dim, cc	44.97	52.18	0.7046	0.0278	0.1627	0.4028
VGG16 32 dim, GAN	43.98	51.92	0.7049	0.0516	0.2222	0.4544
VGG16 32 dim, GAN, cc	42.95	50.58	0.7145	0.0417	0.2222	0.4603
VGG16 64 dim	41.77	48.55	0.7201	0.0278	0.1865	0.4425
VGG16 64 dim, cc	42.72	49.68	0.7153	0.0298	0.1865	0.4286
VGG16 64 dim, GAN	40.96	48.15	0.7153	0.0437	0.2222	0.4623
VGG16 64 dim, GAN, cc	40.20	47.45	0.7239	0.0417	0.2282	0.4881
VGG16 128 dim	44.17	51.14	0.7024	0.0278	0.1647	0.4067
VGG16 128 dim, cc	38.63	45.06	0.7442	0.0238	0.2063	0.4861
VGG16 128 dim, GAN	40.41	47.84	0.7279	0.0615	0.2302	0.4901
VGG16 128 dim, GAN, cc	39.46	46.71	0.7417	0.0556	0.2262	0.5060
VGG(128)+ ResNet(128), GAN	36.93	42.92	0.7566	0.0377	0.2282	0.4980
VGG(128)+From-scratch, GAN, cc	31.78	36.85	0.7735	0.0476	0.2599	0.6310

Table 4: Performance metrics for models with and without GAN, evaluated in 100m radius. Cc stands for cross-correlation, and the others were calculated with cosine similarity.

Figure 11: Distribution of the top 1 prediction error in meters evaluated in 500, 200 and 100m radius around the true drone locations without and with applying CycleGAN. The ensemble model is the average of the two best-performing models, which are VGG16 with 128 bottleneck size and ResNet50 with 128 bottleneck size with GAN in the cosine distance part, while VGG16 with 128 bottleneck size and the from-scratch model with GAN when considering cross-correlation.

These results show that ensemble models can improve performance, with the combination of two models outperforming either model individually. However, using ensemble models in this context introduces practical limitations: not only must both models be stored and used on the drone, but the latent vectors of all satellite images in the grid must also be stored encoded by both models during the flight. This increases memory requirements and slows down the evaluation process.

Figure 12: Top- $p\%$ accuracy curve of the models evaluated in 500, 200 and 100m radius around the true drone locations without and with applying CycleGAN. The ensemble model is the average of the two best-performing models, which are VGG16 with 128 bottleneck size and ResNet50 with 128 bottleneck size with GAN in the cosine distance part, while VGG16 with 128 bottleneck size and the from-scratch model with GAN when considering cross-correlation.

Figure 13 shows examples of images with errors less than 10 and more than 190m in the 200m evaluation radius using the VGG16 model with a bottleneck size of 128 without CycleGAN. The set of best-recognized images mostly includes images showing borders between objects that have distinct textures and colors. In contrast, the model struggled most with images showing homogeneous forest areas and scenes where the landscape had changed between the time of capturing the satellite and UAV images.

Because all error distributions peaked around 30m, I examined the test images with prediction errors close to this value. Some examples are shown in Figure 14. These visualizations reveal that the top-1 predictions are nearly perfect, while the ground truth locations are slightly shifted, suggesting some inaccuracy in the drone sensors. This finding implies that the actual model performance may be better than indicated by the evaluation metrics presented above.

Figure 13: Sample images recognized with less than 10m and more than 190m error in 200m radius by VGG16 model with 128 bottleneck size.

Figure 14: Sample images that have 30m error in 200m radius by VGG16 model with 64 bottleneck size using GAN, where the prediction is more similar to the original image than the ground truth.

7 Conclusions

In this thesis, I addressed UAV localization in GPS-denied environments using camera-based methods. I focused on real-time localization with low storage and computational overhead aiming to overcome challenges such as appearance changes due to lighting, season, and viewpoint differences between UAV and satellite imagery.

The core of my approach involved using autoencoders to compress satellite images into latent space representations, enabling efficient matching with drone images easier. I developed and compared both from-scratch convolutional autoencoders and pre-trained encoder-based models: VGG16, EfficientNet-B0, and ResNet50. In addition, I applied a CycleGAN model to improve alignment between UAV and satellite images by minimizing appearance differences. To evaluate performance, I used cosine similarity and cross-correlation as distance metrics between latent vectors. Model effectiveness was assessed across 100m, 200m, and 500m radius neighborhoods using MAE, RMSE, top p% accuracy and NDCG@15.

Among pre-trained models, VGG16 with 128-dimensional bottleneck without GAN, using cosine similarity, performed best in most metrics, achieving an MAE of 61.76m at 200m radius. Another noteworthy stand-alone model was the symmetric from-scratch autoencoder combined with CycleGAN using cross-correlation, which, despite performing poorly under cosine distance, outperformed all other models when evaluated with cross-correlation. The best overall performance came from an ensemble model combining VGG16 without GAN and from-scratch model with GAN evaluated using cross-correlation. This model achieved an MAE of 31.78m, a RMSE of 36.85m at 100m radius, 45.33m MAE and 65.86m RMSE at 200m radius, and 97.80m MAE and 167.14m RMSE at 500m radius. Its top 1% accuracy reached 73% at 500m radius, and it had an NDCG@15 value up to 0.8674, indicating high ranking accuracy. CycleGAN consistently improved alignment, especially for models not based on VGG.

Results show that higher-dimensional latent vectors consistently outperform lower-dimensional ones. Additionally, pre-trained encoders offer more robust feature extraction than from-scratch networks, and cross-correlation is more effective than cosine similarity for some architectures. CycleGAN is particularly useful when UAV and satellite images differ significantly in lighting or seasonal conditions.

Although combining two different models led to a higher accuracy in localization, this approach requires twice as much memory storage compared to using a single method, and it also increases computational time. Localization accuracy still has room for improvement. However, it is important to emphasize that this study used a new, unfiltered database instead of a well-known, clean benchmark dataset, so

results are not directly comparable with findings discussed in the Related Work section.

In the future, I plan to explore Vision Transformer-based encoders for a potentially better feature extraction. I also intend to reduce the latent dimensions while maintaining the same accuracy, and to integrate IMU and visual odometry data through sensor fusion. Enhancing training with multi-seasonal datasets to improve invariance is another promising direction to improve robustness.

Ultimately, this work demonstrates that combining classical representation learning with generative models can significantly advance UAV localization under realistic and challenging conditions. The methods developed here could be adapted to real-world drone systems operating in regions where GPS signals are unreliable or absent. With further refinement and integration of complementary data sources, this approach holds great promise for reliable GPS-independent navigation.

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